

Anxiety and Sports Performance: Perceptibility of National Players

Muhammad Iftikhar, Basit Ansari, Iqra Rizwan, Nabeela Shakur Abbasi, Shahnila Tariq

Article Info

Article History

Received:
April 25, 2022

Accepted:
November 29, 2022

Keywords :

Sports Anxiety, Worry,
Concentration
Disruption, Somatic
Anxiety.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.7374160

Abstract

This study aimed to evaluate the impact of anxiety on the perception about the performance of the national athletes. It was hypothesized that anxiety will positively affect the performance of the athletes. The sample consisted of 350 national athletes. Data were collected using non-probability convenient sampling technique from four provinces of Pakistan (Punjab, KPK, Sindh and Balochistan). Data were collected using the Sports Anxiety Scale-2 (SAS-2; Smith et al., 2006) and performance was measured through the number of medals won by the athlete. The results suggest that exercise anxiety reduces the performance of the national players/athletes.

Introduction

Anxiety is an emotion that manifests as an unpleasant state of inner confusion, including subjectively unpleasant feelings and emotions related to anticipated events (Robazza & Ruiz, 2018). The nervous system most often has this condition, such as pacing back and forth, physical discomfort, feelings of anxiety and restlessness. Muscle tension, fatigue, anxiety, breathing problems, and trouble concentrating are also common (Lozano, et al., 2022; Samuelson, 2021). Anxiety and fear are closely related. This is an immediate response to a real or perceived threat. Concerns include the prospect of winning or losing. People with anxiety disorders do not engage in situations that may have caused anxiety in the past. Anxiety is often a human response that worsens more persistently than necessary (Stokes, 2019; Taschereau-Dumouchel et al., 2022). There are many types of anxiety disorders (such as generalized anxiety disorder and obsessive-compulsive disorder) that have specific medical definitions. Anxiety is a complicated thing. We are all interested to know this. We want to know why we act and why we react. Why do we feel scared, bad or happy? Some of us can complete tasks quickly, while others take a long time to complete tasks. Some of these questions come to mind because we want to better understand human nature, attitudes, and experiences. Anxiety research allows us to answer these questions scientifically (Barlow, 2019; Fernandez et al., 2019; Gardner et al., 2019; Perrotta, 2019). The term anxiety is associated with the study of human behavior, while sports anxiety is a subcategory of psychology that deals with the anxiety of athletes and teams involved in competitive sports. Sports anxiety is a branch of psychology that is closely related to human anxiety on the sports field, both in practice and in the context of competition, in order to maintain a qualitative improvement in performance and maintain the same in competition anxiety. Anxiety is a common emotional state and worry of any kind. This is an unpleasant psychological response to the perceived stress of performing a stressful task. This is what all athletes experience performance-wise. Athletes also care about winning or performing well in their sport. That's what a player thinks, they can win or not, so when there's anxiety, it's physical and mental. Anxiety is often divided into a range of physical (sweating, shaking, feeling weak or tired, increased heart rate) and psychological (loss of control, negative expectations, worry and self-care) Anxiety is the study of human behavior/attitudes that emphasize psychological aspects of anxiety in the sports environment (Fernandez et al., 2019).

Objective of the Study

Determining the effect of anxiety on the performance of the national athlete.

Rationale of the Study

National athletes have to face stressful situations during competition and final stages. Therefore, it is important to understand how athletes feel before a match. This research will be useful for athletes and future researchers.

Operational Definition

Anxiety is a general term for several disorders that cause nervousness, fear, apprehension, and worrying. These disorders affect how we feel and behave and can cause physical symptoms.

Methodology

Using a cross-sectional survey design, this study was conducted in four provinces of Pakistan. The sample size was 350 national athletes (according to the Rao-Soft formula) using a non-probability sampling technique. (SAS) Exercise Anxiety Scale (Smith, 2006) was used to collect data and analyze the data by SPSS.

Results

Figure: 01

Figure 01, shows that athletes' self-doubts, choking under pressure, worried about reaching goal and disappointment.

Figure: 02

According to Figure, 02 athletes thinking unrelated things during competition, mind wander, nervousness and do not pay attention to what's going on.

Figure: 03

Figure, 03 shows that athletes feel nervous, feel tense, tense in stomach, heart races, stomach sinking, feel tight, heart pounds and stomach gets upset during competition

Table: 01

The Sports Anxiety scale

Domains	Sample	Mean	±Std. D
Worry	350	4.89	±1.52
Concentration Disruption	350	4.71	±1.37
Somatic Anxiety	350	4.67	±1.32
Total	350	4.75	±1.40

Table, 02 shows that the $\pm$ SD values of all factors are close around the mean and the data are clustered closely around the mean.

Discussion:

Previous research has been devoted to understanding how anxiety affects athletic performance, both in practice and in competitive settings (Cottrell et al., 2019; Lopes Dos Santos et al., 2020). Exercise is known to be associated with high levels of stress and anxiety, and practicing and using a range of psychological strategies can be beneficial for managing anxiety. More specifically, the findings provide readers with definitions and theoretical conceptualizations of exercise-related anxiety. Next, by including performance activities, it will be argued that the term "performance" is broader than activities related to sports-related practices and performance in competitions. This article highlights the importance of recognizing early signs and symptoms of anxiety and the potential need for referral. Finally, the findings highlight the need for appropriate, client-specific, and competent care for athletes experiencing sports-related anxiety. The findings also match previous studies describing what happens if you struggle with anxiety and feel it negatively impacts your athletic performance (Campo et al., 2018; Hetland, 2022; Oblinger-Peters & Krenn, 2020). Current research shows that anxiety has a negative impact on the performance of national athletes, and it may be because most athletes do not have the ability to cope with exercise anxiety. This affects their overall performance too.

Conclusion

Based on the results, the researchers concluded that anxiety had a negative impact on the performance of national athletes. All of the key concepts about exercise anxiety are closely related. Athlete self-doubt, suffocation under pressure, worry about achieving goals and disappointment. Athletes think about unrelated things during the game, get distracted, get nervous and not pay attention to what is going on. Athletes feel jittery, jittery, tight, heart pounding, stomach sinking, feeling tense, heart racing, upset stomach during competition. So, these factors need to be taken care of in order to improve their performance.

References

- Barlow, D. H. (2019). The dimensions of anxiety disorders. In *Anxiety and the anxiety disorders* (pp. 479-500). Routledge.
- Campo, M., Martinent, G., Pellet, J., Boulanger, J., Louvet, B., & Nicolas, M. (2018). Emotion–performance relationships in team sport: The role of personal and social identities. *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, 13(5), 629-635.
- Cottrell, C., McMillen, N., & Harris, B. S. (2019). Sport psychology in a virtual world: Considerations for practitioners working in eSports. *Journal of Sport Psychology in Action*, 10(2), 73-81.
- Fernandez, M. M., Bello, F. D., Barreto, L. B. M., Brito, C. J., Miarka, B., & Diaz-de-Durana, A. L. (2019). State-trait anxiety and reduced emotional intelligence in combat sport athletes of different genders and competitive levels. *Journal of Physical Education and Sport*, 19(Suppl. 2), 363-368.
- Hetland, A. (2022). Feeling and Thinking about It Are Two Different Things: How to Capture Momentary Emotions of Extreme Sports in the Field. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(3), 1290.
- Lopes Dos Santos, M., Uftring, M., Stahl, C. A., Lockie, R. G., Alvar, B., Mann, J. B., & Dawes, J. J. (2020). Stress in academic and athletic performance in collegiate athletes: A narrative review of sources and monitoring strategies. *Frontiers in Sports and Active Living*, 2, 42.
- Lozano, R., Thompson, T., Dixon-Weber, J., Erickson, C. A., Berry-Kravis, E., Williams, S., ... & Hessler, D. (2022). Observable Symptoms of Anxiety in Individuals with Fragile X Syndrome: Parent and Caregiver Perspectives. *Genes*, 13(9), 1660.
- Oblinger-Peters, V., & Krenn, B. (2020). “Time for recovery” or “utter uncertainty”? The postponement of the Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games through the eyes of Olympic athletes and coaches. A qualitative study. *Frontiers in psychology*, 11, 610856.
- Perrotta, G. (2019). Anxiety disorders: definitions, contexts, neural correlates and strategic therapy. *J NeurNeurosci*, 6(1), 042.
- Robazza, C., & Ruiz, M. C. (2018). Oxford research encyclopedia of psychology.
- Samuelson, M. (2021). Degenerative Diseases of the Central Nervous System. *Early's Physical Dysfunction Practice Skills for the Occupational Therapy Assistant E-Book*, 461.
- Smith, R. E., Smoll, F. L., Cumming, S. P., & Grossbard, J. R. (2006). Measurement of multidimensional sport performance anxiety in children and adults: The Sport Anxiety Scale-2. *Journal of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 28(4), 479-501.
- Stokes, P. E. (2019). The neuroendocrinology of anxiety. *Anxiety and the anxiety disorders*, 53-76.
- Taschereau-Dumouchel, V., Michel, M., Lau, H., Hofmann, S. G., & LeDoux, J. E. (2022). Putting the “mental” back in “mental disorders”: a perspective from research on fear and anxiety. *Molecular Psychiatry*, 27(3), 1322-1330.

Author Information

Muhammad Iftikhar, Ph.D. Scholar

Health Physical Education, and Sports Sciences,
University of Karachi, Pakistan.

Dr. Basit Ansari

Associate Professor, Chairman, Department of Health
Physical Education and Sports Sciences, University
of Karachi, Pakistan.

Iqra Rizwan

Lecturer in Educational sciences Department of
National University of modern languages Islamabad

Nabeela Shakur Abbasi

Lecturer Department of Educational Sciences NUML.

Dr Shahnaila Tariq

Associate Professor, Department of Applied
Psychology, University of Management and
Technology (UMT), Lahore, Pakistan.
